

COMPETENCY SKILLS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF CANDELARIA EAST DISTRICT: BASIS FOR PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The key objective of the study was to assess whether professional development has an important role in improving teachers' competency skills in their profession. The proposed professional development program was one of several strategies for improving teacher growth and competency. It gave teachers the opportunity to participate in a variety of activities, including workshops, seminars, training sessions, and collaborative learning experiences. These activities aimed to improve their teaching tactics, content understanding, classroom management abilities, and overall pedagogical practices. This study utilized mixed method research designs. The respondents of this study were 176 elementary teachers who are currently teaching in eight (15) elementary schools of Candelaria East District, Division of Quezon, in School Year 2023-2024. The researcher utilized survey questionnaire through google forms in gathering the needed data. The level of the competency skills of the respondents in terms of decision making and professional judgment were very satisfactory, instructions were outstanding and research and experience were very satisfactory. Study revealed a significant relationship between respondent profile factors such as age, sex, and length of service and their level of competency in decision-making and professional judgment, instruction, research, and experience. In educational attainment, decision making, and professional judgment, research and experience have a significant relationship, however for instruction there is no significant relationship. Teachers actively seek out various techniques to stay current on educational trends. The

researcher recommends to teachers to develop and attend professional development courses. Other needs analysis relevant factors may also be considered.

Keywords: *Professional development, competency skills*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a vital and complex role in education. They are in charge of establishing a supportive and encouraging learning environment that fosters success, success, and growth. Teachers help students learn, create engaging lessons, mentor and inspire them, monitor their progress, inspire collaboration and innovation, and speak up for them. A professional teacher's primary responsibility is to deliver efficient education. The teaching profession undergoes constant change due to its dynamic nature. The teacher is the most important agent in the teaching and learning process. However, teachers must constantly advance their abilities and knowledge in order to effectively perform these jobs. Professional development is the continuous process of learning and enhancing one's teaching methods through numerous workshops, conferences, training sessions, and other events. It also gives teachers the chance to work with other teachers and exchange best practices. Teachers can collaborate on projects and efforts, share ideas with other professionals through collaboration possibilities, and improve the performance of students. Teachers who participate in professional development training can improve their time management and organization skills.

Moreover, instead of concentrating on the outcomes of particular professional development activities or initiatives, everyone was more interested in comprehensive descriptions of professional development systems within specific countries and jurisdictions around the world that take into account the various factors that mediate the impact of teacher professional development (e.g., cultural, societal, political, and economic). Cultural factors can impact professional development programs by influencing the attitudes and perceptions of teachers towards the training. Societal factors can impact professional development programs by influencing the attitudes and perceptions of teachers towards the training. Political factors can impact professional development programs by influencing the funding, design, and implementation of training initiatives and economic factors can include funding availability, cost of training, and economic conditions in the broader community. Additionally, Filipino teachers face emotional and occupational stress as a result of their jobs, which has an impact on both their personal and professional growth (Bongo and Casta, 2017). In order to emphasize individuals who exhibit the desired leadership qualities, teacher leadership focuses on teachers' ability to provide answers to problems that arise (Oracion, 2014).

Irembere (2019), discovered that Filipino teachers are simply considered to be "implementers of the curriculum" and strongly suggested that they be at the center of the planning and design of curricula. These initiatives in the planning of teachers professional development for Filipino teachers can be viewed as promising ones. In a

related study, Gutierrez and Kim (2017), discovered that four qualities—collaboration, sustainability, trust, and commitment—are fostered as teachers conduct research to improve their own instructional techniques.

In addition, the larger goal of enhancing teaching policy and practice in education is to raise standards and increase social growth capacity. Professional development is a critical element within this larger agenda. The teaching process includes a challenging but essential component known as teacher professional development. It's critical to track teachers' professional growth and research how occupational standards and teacher competency interact in the actual classroom environment.

Likewise, professional development is a critical component of the larger agenda of raising standards and increasing societal growth capacity through improved educational policy and practice. Teacher professional development is a complex, yet necessary component of the teaching process. It is critical to monitor teachers' development and investigate how teacher competency, in connection with occupational standards, works in the actual teaching process. Through a variety of initiatives, the Philippine government has consistently pursued teacher quality reforms. The National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) were formalized as a framework for teacher quality by CHED Memorandum Order No. 52, s. 2007 as well as DepED Order No. 32, s. 2009.

As stated in a study, professional teachers interact with students, colleagues, school officials, and community leaders on a daily basis. Concerning the teacher's professional strengths and needs, he discovered that they are weak on planning, assessing, reporting, and personal growth, but strong on social regard for learning, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum, and community linkages. On the other hand, the teaching competence of teachers is highly regarded as the core of every educational endeavor. Educators worldwide are greatly challenged to gradually develop a more complex teaching competence due to the demand for highly skilled graduates in the global market. As stated in DM no.008, s. 2023 titled Multi-Year Guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System-Philippine.

Also, Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST) covers the contained procedure as well as all relevant information on the adoption and implementation of performance management and teacher appraisal. The tools, forms, and protocols outlined in this document are being developed and modified to ensure that the measures of teacher performance used over the next three school years are appropriate, adaptive, and relevant to capturing teachers' actual performance and are applicable to all contexts and scenarios encountered by schools using various learning modalities.

Based on the premises mentioned, the researcher conducted a study to investigate the relationship between professional development and teachers' competency skills. The main objective of the study was to determine whether professional development plays a significant role in enhancing teachers' competency in their profession. The proposed professional development program served as one of the solutions for enhancing teacher development and competency. It provided teachers with

opportunities to engage in various activities, such as workshops, seminars, training sessions, and collaborative learning experiences. These activities focused on improving their instructional strategies, content knowledge, classroom management skills, and overall pedagogical practices.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the competency skills of Public Elementary School Teachers of Candelaria East District.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. educational attainment;
 - 1.4. length in service;
 - 1.5. teaching position?
2. What is the level of competency skills of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. decision-making and professional judgment;
 - 2.2. instruction;
 - 2.3. research and experience;
3. What opportunities to learn?
4. Is there a significant relationship between respondent's profile and their level of competency skills of the Public Elementary School Teachers of Candelaria East District?
5. Based from the findings of the study, what professional development program can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

The mixed method research used to determine the significant relationship between respondent's profile and competency skills.

According to Creswell (2012), a mixed methods research design is a procedure for collecting, analyzing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative methods in a study for purposes of understanding a research problem. In order to obtain data, the researcher made a self-made questionnaire regarding profile of respondents such as age, gender, length of service, and adapted questionnaires as the respondent's level of

teaching competency, such as decision-making and professional judgment, instruction, research and experience, and opportunities to learn. To be more specific, a Google Forms survey used to collect data for statistical analysis.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Candelaria East District schools. This study included 176 public elementary school teachers from Candelaria East District.

This school year 2023-2024, Candelaria East District has 15 Public Elementary Schools with a total of 321 teaching personnel. The researcher chose respondents using random sampling.

Research Instrument

The research instruments utilized in this study were survey questionnaires regarding the respondent's demographic profile and their competency skills.

The questionnaire focuses on two parts. The first part was the respondent's profile such sex, age, length of service, and teaching position. The second part was the respondent's level of teaching competence such as decision-making and professional judgment, instruction, research and experience, opportunities to learn. The researcher adapted the questionnaire of Rabano, (2021) about the variables under teaching competence.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher asked permission from Schools Division Superintendent through a letter of request to conduct a research. The researcher requested permission from the Public Schools District Supervisor of Candelaria East District to conduct research and to have formal endorsement to school heads. As part of the conduct of the study, Data Sharing Agreement prepared by the researcher and signed by the authorized personnel in the division. The researcher also wrote a letter addressed to the Planning Section of the Division of Quezon to request for a complete list of the public elementary school in the division per district with corresponding principal's name, their contact numbers and the email address of the school for accurate information needed in this study. Through a letter, the researcher adapted the questionnaire in the teaching competence of Rabano, 2021 from the study Level of Professional Standards in Learning Delivery: Accounting to the Professional Commitment and Teaching Competence of Secondary School Teachers.

This study used Google Forms to administer the instrument, which was approved by the school principal. Since it used Google Forms, the data was collected in a CSV file and subjected to appropriate statistical treatment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Following completion of the survey, all data was collected, collated, and statistically analyzed. The study presents the profile of the respondents using

Frequency and Percent Distribution. The respondents' level of teaching competence determined using the Weighted/Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviation. Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) will be used to determine the significant relationship between respondent's profile and the level of competency skills.

RESULTS

This part of the study shows the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents which sought to answer the following questions posited on the objectives of the study.

1. Profile of the Respondents.

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents

Profile Variable	Frequenc y	Percentag e	Ran k
Age:			
30 years old and below	37	21.02	3
31 - 40 years old	58	32.95	1.5
41 - 50 years old	58	32.95	1.5
51 years old and above	23	13.07	4
Total	176	100	
Sex:			
Female	146	82.95	1
Male	30	17.05	2
Total	176	100	
Educational attainment:			
Bachelor's Degree	56	31.82	2

With MA Units	69	39.20	1
Master Degree Holder	45	25.57	3
With Doctorate Units	3	1.70	4.5
Doctorate Degree Holder	3	1.70	4.5
Total	176	100	
Length of Service:			
1 - 10 years	90	51.14	1
11 - 20 years	44	25.00	2
21 - 30 years	31	17.61	3
31 years and above	11	6.25	4
Total	176	100	
Teaching Position:			
Teacher I	70	39.77	1
Teacher II	52	29.55	2
Teacher III	43	24.43	3
SPED Teacher	2	1.14	5
Master Teacher	9	5.11	4
Total	176	100	

As stated in Table 1, in terms of the age range of the respondents, 31 - 40 and 41 - 50 years old made the highest equal frequency counts of 58 or 32.95% at rank 1.5 while 51 years old and above got the least frequency count of 23 or 13.07% at rank 4.

For the sexes of the chosen respondents, 146 of them or 82.95% at rank 1 were female while male got 30 or 17.05% at rank 2. According to the Philippine Commission on Women (2014), as of 2008–2009, 89.58% of the teachers in public elementary schools are female and the number of female teachers in the place where the study administered was greater than male teachers.

With respect to the respondents' educational attainment, With Masteral Units garnered the highest frequency count of 69 or 39.20% at rank 1 while With Doctorate Units and Doctorate Degree Holder made the least equal frequency counts of three or 1.70% at ranks 4.5.

In Terms of the respondents' length of service, 1 - 10 years yielded the highest frequency count of 90 or 51.14% at rank 1 whereas 31 years and above got the least frequency count of 11 or 6.25% at rank 4.

Finally, in terms of teaching position, Teacher I got the highest frequency count of 70 or 39.77% at rank 1 while Special Education Teacher obtained the least frequency count of two or 1.14% at rank 5.

Level of Competency Skills of Teachers.

1. In Terms of Decision Making and Professional Judgment

Table 2

Level of Competency Skills of Teachers in Terms of Decision Making and Professional Judgement

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>I have...</i>			
1. prepared and submitted regularly daily lesson plan based on Most Essential Learning Competencies	4.32	Outstanding	1
2 maximized the use of ICT	4.04	Very Satisfactory	7
3 facilitated active learning through innovative teaching strategies and differentiated instruction	4.10	Very Satisfactory	6
4 paced lessons appropriate to the needs and difficulties of individual learners and used varied strategies which consider diversity	4.14	Very Satisfactory	4
5 carried out efficiently the planning, implementing and evaluation phases of teaching-learning process	4.13	Very Satisfactory	5

6 initiated successful discipline of students, including rules and guidelines for individual or group tasks	4.24	Outstanding	2
7 established routines and procedures to maximize the use of time and instructional materials	4.22	Outstanding	3
Composite Mean	4.17	Very Satisfactory	

As reflected in Table 2, the teacher-respondents replied that they have outstandingly prepared and submitted regularly daily lesson plan based on Most Essential Learning Competencies which gained the highest weighted mean of 4.32 and the highest rank of 1. It indicates that teachers submitted daily lesson plans, which may assist the school principal in understanding the competencies, sequence of the lesson, activities, resources, and materials to be used during the discussion, and how to deliver the lesson properly by the teacher.

Lesson planning is a key step before beginning the learning process. It helps teachers organize their teaching strategies and avoid mistakes (Neisari & Heidari, 2014; Planet, 2015). Based from Strong (2021) lesson planning is essential for effective teaching and learning.

On the other hand, the said group of respondents answered that they very satisfactorily maximized the use of ICT which made the least weighted mean of 4.04 and least rank of 7. The use of ICT or technologies is essential in teaching since it allows teachers to increase their competency abilities and provide lessons in innovative ways. The use of ICT allows teachers to have more access to instructional resources and improves their productivity. According to Almerich et al. (2016), teachers' ICT competencies play a crucial role in incorporating technology into their instructional practices.

The overall achieved composite mean of 4.17 implied that the teacher-respondents' level of competency skills in terms of decision making and professional judgement were very satisfactory. This signifies that the teachers displayed a high level of proficiency and effectiveness while making decisions and applying professional judgment at work. Their capacity to analyze circumstances, weigh many considerations, and draw sound conclusions was admirable. This level of competency implies that the teachers have the abilities and knowledge to make sound decisions and use professional judgment in their teaching practices. Based from Van Phung, et al. (2018) teacher decision-making is critical to effective learning and teaching. A variety of research papers show the impact of teacher decision-making processes on improving student learning.

2.2. In Terms of Instruction.

Table 3

Level of Competency Skills of Teachers in Terms of Instruction

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>I have...</i>			
1. monitored and evaluated efficiently students' progress	4.44	Outstanding	1
0. initiated enrichment program for advanced students to further enhance their performance	4.23	Outstanding	7
3. conducted remediation program and appropriate intervention activities for learners at-risk to help them improve their performance	4.27	Outstanding	5
4. maintained updated and accurate students' scholastic records	4.40	Outstanding	2
5. provided timely feedback on student's assessment	4.24	Outstanding	6
6. employed project and portfolio assessment methods that display student learning	4.15	Very Satisfactory	9
7. used both traditional and authentic methods to assess students' performance	4.30	Outstanding	3
8. capitalized on the use of teacher-made scoring rubrics in rating process-oriented and product-oriented performances	4.18	Very Satisfactory	8
9. created appropriate formative and summative tests that measure target competencies	4.28	Outstanding	4
Composite Mean	4.27	Outstanding	

As written in Table 3, the teacher-respondents acknowledged that they have outstandingly monitored and evaluated efficiently students' progress which obtained the

highest weighted mean of 4.44 and the highest rank of 1. It implies that student progress monitoring will assist teachers in evaluating the effectiveness of their instruction and determining the level of performance of their students. The teacher always assesses students mastery of certain learning materials and adjusts the following learning activities suitably. According to Pierce, (2002; cited in Kırmızı & Kömeç, 2016), effective evaluation is essential for successful learning and teaching. It guides daily teaching decisions, identifies student strengths and deficiencies, and gives personalized feedback to enhance learning. Evaluation also provides teachers with timely feedback to adapt their teaching approaches based on their students' learning styles. The process of monitoring and evaluating student progress is closely connected to the professional development of a teacher. Through the analysis of student performance data, teachers can gain valuable insights into the effectiveness of their teaching methods. This information can then be used to inform and guide the teacher's professional development, enabling them to continually improve their instructional practices and better support their students.

Meanwhile, the said group of respondents replied that they very satisfactorily employed project and portfolio assessment methods that display student learning which garnered the least weighted mean of 4.15 and least rank of 9. Project and portfolio assessment approaches are frequently used by teachers to document student learning based on specific curriculum outcomes. Portfolios provide a comprehensive assessment of students' development and accomplishments, encompassing all aspects of their classroom activities. Based from Lam (2015) portfolio and project assessments can be used by teachers as feedback to improve the teaching-learning process and by students as learning tools to track their progress.

The computed composite mean of 4.27 affirmed that the teacher-respondents' level of competency skills in terms of instructions were outstanding. The high level of instruction competency skills indicates that the teacher's respondents had an adequate basis of knowledge and skills required for effective teaching. They displayed knowledge in a variety of areas of instructional practice, enabling them to provide meaningful and powerful learning experiences for their students. Teachers should have functional competency, which includes knowledge of teaching and learning, assessment, communication, questioning techniques, and evaluation of student performance (Malaysian Education Ministry, 2014).

2.3. In Terms of Research and Experience.

Table 4

Level of Competency Skills of Teachers in Terms of Research and Experience

Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>I have...</i>			
1. conducted relevant and purposeful action researches	3.44	Very Satisfactory	4
2. initiated innovation/s related to the profession	3.58	Very Satisfactory	3
3. earned or completed units in the graduate school program	3.60	Very Satisfactory	2
4. produced publications or creative works in the school or division level	3.18	Satisfactory	6
5. received special awards or recognition for exemplary performance and/or engagement in professional events	3.35	Satisfactory	5
6. reflected consistently on the quality of teaching, vis-à-vis learning outcomes, and used valid assessment tools to better performance	3.70	Very Satisfactory	1
Composite Mean	3.48	Very Satisfactory	

As reported in Table 4, the teacher-respondents replied that they have very satisfactorily reflected consistently on the quality of teaching, vis-à-vis learning outcomes, and used valid assessment tools to better performance which made the highest weighted mean of 3.70 and the highest rank of 1. In a daily classroom scenario, the teacher regularly evaluates their teaching quality and its impact on learning results. They employ valid assessment tools to enhance their performance. This reflection and use of evaluation methods help to promote continuing professional development and improve student learning. According to Paolini (2015), using methods of evaluation to measure teaching effectiveness can greatly benefit education. Enhancing the assessment tool for

teachers will increase the teachers' competence in the teaching-learning process, which students will undoubtedly enjoy.

On the other hand, the said group of respondents perceived that they have satisfactorily produced publications or creative works in the school or division level which got the least weighted mean of 3.18 and least rank of 6. Teachers believe they have made a successful contribution by developing publications or creative works for the school or division. As cited by Kaplan (2019), creativity is vital for innovation, uniqueness, and sustainability.

The overall achieved composite mean of 3.48 signified that the teacher-respondents' level of competency skills in terms of research and experience were very satisfactory. This level of skill would have enabled them to incorporate research findings into their teaching practices, draw on their professional experiences, engage in reflective practice, and communicate with peers. Overall, their sufficient degree of research and experience helps them develop professionally and improve their instructional approaches. As cited by Dangara (2016), the necessity of professional advancement for educators through various training stages and enrolling in graduate studies is to hone their current abilities or aid them in producing specific abilities that could upgrade their level of creativity and development.

Relationship Between the Profile of the Teacher-Respondents and Their Level of Competency Skills.

Table 5

Relationship Between the Profile of the Teacher-Respondents and Their Level of Competency Skills

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age:				
Decision Making and Professional Judgment	-0.27	0.00029	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Instruction	-0.26	0.00049	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Research and Experience	-0.36	9.20E-7	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

Sex:					
Decision Making and Professional Judgment	0.30	0.00005	Reject Ho	Highly Significant	
Instruction	0.29	0.00009	Reject Ho	Highly Significant	
Research and Experience	0.26	0.00049	Reject Ho	Highly Significant	
Educational Attainment:					
Decision Making and Professional Judgment	0.17	0.02409	Reject Ho	Significant	
Instruction	0.04	0.59813	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant	
Research and Experience	0.26	0.00049	Reject Ho	Highly Significant	
Length of Service:					
Decision Making and Professional Judgment	-0.24	0.00134	Reject Ho	Highly Significant	
Instruction	-0.23	0.00213	Reject Ho	Highly Significant	
Research and Experience	-0.33	7.72E-6	Reject Ho	Highly Significant	
Teaching Position:					
Decision Making and Professional Judgment	-0.01	0.89520	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant	
Instruction	-0.14	0.06385	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant	
Research and Experience	-0.05	0.50989	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant	

As given in Table 5, when the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents were compared to their ages, the computed r-values of -0.27 for decision

making and professional judgment, -0.26 for instruction, and -0.36 for research and experience have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These safely concluded that the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents have high indirect significant relationships in terms of decision making and professional judgment, instruction, and research and experience when compared to their ages. As teachers get older, they tend to build and polish their competencies. This accumulation of knowledge frequently results in a greater grasp of instructional strategies, enhanced classroom management skills, and better decision-making ability. Based on the study of Nyagah and Gathumbi (2017), older teachers were more likely to increase their students' learning outcomes than middle-aged and younger teachers.

Moreover, when the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents were compared to their sexes, the computed r-values of 0.30 for decision making and professional judgment, 0.29 for instruction, and 0.26 for research and experience have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These safely generalized that the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents have high direct significant relationships in terms of decision making and professional judgment, instruction, and research and experience when compared to their sexes. Several studies have looked into potential differences in teaching styles, communication approaches, and classroom management techniques between male and female teachers. According to Lourdes Machado-Taylor et al. (2014), they discovered female teachers were less satisfied with their personal and professional development than male teachers, especially with the balance between work and home.

Furthermore, when the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents were compared to their educational attainments, the computed r-value of 0.26 for research and experience has a corresponding p-value of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. In addition, the computed r-value of 0.17 for decision making and professional judgement has a corresponding p-value of less than 0.5, thus rejecting also the hypothesis. Meanwhile, the computed r-value of 0.04 for instruction has a corresponding p-value of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These safely deduced that the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents have high direct significant relationship in terms research and experience; direct significant relationship in terms of decision making and professional judgment, and no direct significant relationship in terms of instruction when compared to their educational attainments. Additionally, when the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents were compared to their length of services, the computed r-values of -0.24 for decision making and professional judgment, -0.23 for instruction, and -0.33 for research and experience have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These safely generalized that the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents have high indirect significant relationships in terms of decision making and professional judgment, instruction, and research and experience when compared to their

length of services. Teachers who have been in the profession for a longer period of time have typically gained more experience, developed successful teaching strategies, and mastered their classroom management skills. This additional experience and exposure to different teaching circumstances can help you gain a better understanding of student needs, refine your instructional strategies, and improve your overall classroom competency. Latiff et al. (2017) studied how teacher experience level impacts job satisfaction. The study found that experience or length of service increased work satisfaction.

Lastly, when the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents were compared to their teaching positions, the computed r-values of -0.01 for decision making and professional judgment, -0.14 for instruction, and -0.05 for research and experience have corresponding p-values of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These safely judged that the level of competency skills of the teacher-respondents have high no indirect significant relationships in terms of decision making and professional judgment, instruction, and research and experience when compared to their teaching positions. Competency skills are critical for teachers to properly carry out their roles and obligations in the classroom. However, this study found no apparent connection between these skills and teaching positions.

Responses of the Teacher-respondents Views on How they update themselves with the recent developments in education

Teachers use a variety of strategies to stay current on educational trends. Participating in professional development programs such as trainings, seminars, and workshops. Reading books, articles, and publications about education. Collaborating with others to share best practices and instructional materials. Enrolling in postgraduate study to expand your subject-specific knowledge. Conducting research to discover new teaching practices and contribute to educational progress.

These approaches assist teachers in staying up to date on new teaching methods, pedagogical approaches, and innovative educational technologies, leading to continuous improvement in their competency skills. Guerriero (2017), define the continuous improvement of competencies (knowledge, skills, and attitudes) that may lead to (or not) additional formal results in a teacher's career (e.g. continuing professional development).

Responses of the Teacher-respondents Views on the opportunities given by their institution for them to be updated on the field

Institutions offer professional development programs to help teachers improve their skills. These programs may include trainings, seminars, and workshops centered on modern teaching methods, classroom management strategies, and cutting-edge educational technologies. These programs also provide insights into subject-specific topic knowledge and pedagogical practices, allowing teachers to renew their abilities and keep up with contemporary educational trends. Technical assistance is another option provided by institutions to help teachers apply innovative teaching practices and integrate new

educational technologies. Technical assistance may involve giving access to educational materials, advising and supporting lesson plan development, and encouraging the implementation of innovative teaching approaches.

According to Woodcock and Hardy (2017), teachers engage in a variety of formal and informal activities linked to their professional development. Teachers engage in a wide range of activities to support their professional development. These activities can be formal, such as attending workshops, conferences, or training sessions, as well as informal, like participating in peer learning groups, reflective practices, or self-study. This diverse approach helps educators stay current with best practices and research in education, ultimately benefiting their students' learning experiences

In summary, institutions give opportunities for teachers to keep current in the field of education by offering professional development programs and technical assistance. These chances allow teachers to improve their skills, stay updated on new teaching methods, and use creative teaching practices, resulting in improving student outcomes and overall teaching effectiveness.

Responses of the Teacher-respondents Views on the specific areas they wish to be capacitated with

The teacher-respondents expressed a desire to receive training in specific areas such as teaching pedagogy, classroom management, research, ICT (Information and Communication Technology), and written and oral communication. Improving teaching pedagogy is essential for improving instructional strategies and student engagement. Capacitation in classroom management seeks to foster effective discipline and structure in the school setting. Research capacitation helps teachers do educational research and apply evidence-based approaches. Enhancing ICT abilities enables teachers to incorporate technology into their teaching techniques. Coleman, Gibson, Cotten, Howell-Moroney, and Stringer (2016) argue that effective use of ICT in education shifts the learning environment from teacher-centered to learner-centered. The change from teaching to learning fosters a more participatory and engaging learning environment, transforming teachers from knowledge transmitters to facilitators, navigators, and co-learners.

Teachers who continually develop their communication skills can effectively convey complex concepts, provide constructive feedback, and engage in meaningful dialogue with all stakeholders involved in the educational process. This ultimately contributes to a more enriching and productive learning experience for everyone involved.

Conclusions

Based on the findings as summarized, the following were concluded: 1) The level of the competency skills of the respondents in terms of decision making and professional judgment were very satisfactory, instructions were outstanding and research and

experience were very satisfactory. 2) The study revealed a significant relationship between respondent profile factors such as age, sex, and length of service and their level of competency in decision-making and professional judgment, instruction, research, and experience. In educational attainment, decision making, and professional judgment, research and experience have a significant relationship, however for instruction there is no significant relationship. 3) Teachers actively seek out various techniques to stay current on educational trends, while institutions understand the need of professional development programs to help teachers improve their skills. The indicated desire of teacher responders to acquire training in certain areas demonstrates their dedication to ongoing growth in teaching pedagogy, classroom management, research, ICT, and communication skills.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are offered: 1) Teachers may be attended professional development courses covering modern teaching methods, classroom management, assessment procedures, and subject-specific content knowledge. Motivate the teacher to pursue continuing education alternatives such as graduate degree programs, specialty certificates, or online courses to improve their competency skills. 2) A professional development program might be developed to improve the competency skills of public elementary school teachers in the Candelaria East District based on their needs. This program may include focused training sessions, workshops, mentorship programs, and chances for ongoing learning and growth in the study's identified areas for improvement. 3) Other needs analysis relevant factors may also be considered in crafting the program such as IPCRF results, CO, IPPD etc. 4) Future Researchers may conduct a similar research to determine how teachers' competency skills and professional development are correlated.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To ensure that this study was ethical, the following prioritized. Participants and respondents not harmed in any way as a result of their participation in this study. Full consent gathered from respondents at Candelaria East District Public Elementary School prior to the study. Furthermore, the privacy of research participants and respondents protected. In managing the data, an acceptable amount of detail prevented, as will a biased depiction of main data findings. Furthermore, any affiliations, funding sources, and any conflicts of interest disclosed. Any communication related to this study truthful and transparent.

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